

ME 13 days

NK4 13 days

SB 13 days

$p/\text{sec}/\text{cm}^2/\text{sr}$
Color Scale
Min = $2.00\text{e}6$
Max = $1.60\text{e}7$

ME 20 days

NK4 20 days

SB 20 days

$p/sec/cm^2/sr$

Color Scale
Min = 2.00e6
Max = 1.60e7

→ For Fig. 2

NK4 30 days

SB 30 days

